

THE STRUCTURE OF LINGUISTIC CULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TRANSLATORS AND THE STAGES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11027832>

Abstract: In this article, the composition of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators is studied in detail and the stages of its development are analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, linguistic, communicative, system, improvement, competence, culture, linguistic culture, pedagogy.

INTRODUCTION. It is important to analyze and summarize the results obtained in the pedagogical process aimed at developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators, and to develop a methodology for determining the level of efficiency. Through this, it will be possible to determine the importance of this problem, the pedagogical model of its solution, the conditions and the results achieved through it. The task of improving the system of teaching the national language and culture of the countries whose language is being studied and preparing them for natural communication by developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators is becoming urgent. In this way, information is provided not only about the history, state structure, and national culture of the country whose language is being studied, but on the other hand, in the process of reading texts in foreign languages, specific words (realia), that is, language units without alternatives, phraseological combinations it will be possible to be able to translate aphorisms, to be taught to use speech culture actively and freely in speech communication.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators have been studied by many scientists of the West, the CIS and our country, and even today this process is systematically implemented. Nationality, Linguistic Adequacy, Linguistic, Cultural and Communicative Issues Sh.Abdullayev, I.Vladimirova, M.Javboriyev, Sh.Isakova, N.Isamukhamedova, G.Salomov, I.Komilov, S.Mirzakulov, I.Gafurov, N.Ormonova .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The following types were recommended and described on the basis of different opinions in the scientific-methodical literature about the components of linguistic and cultural and communicative

competence: a) cognitive component; b) operational activity component; c) reflexive component.

Attention was paid to identifying the stages of development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators, and based on the results of the research, we came to the following conclusions:

1. The first stage of developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators. As the first main task at this stage, the development of the knowledge component of linguistic and cultural competence, that is, the acquisition of knowledge about grammatical rules designed to correctly structure speech in a foreign language, and the formation of foreign language communicative skills in various communicative situations. focused on creating an indicator basis for At this stage, the new grammatical material was presented, its linguistic features and content were revealed, and students' attention was drawn to the functioning of the studied grammatical structure in a typical speech text. Acquaintance with new grammatical materials in educational and speech situations was carried out by means of an exhibition (visual), a text in a foreign language, a role-playing game, translation tools, etc., depending on the communicative level and talent level of the students, through induction or deduction methods.

2. The second stage of developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators. At this stage, the student manages the studied linguistic and cultural structure in speech situations typical for his activity. At this stage, the transfer of theoretical knowledge to practical foreign language activities, the development of communicative skills, and the adequacy of the grammar of thought are required. In order to achieve the set goals and objectives, during our research and experimental work, we used types of language exercises, in particular, imitative, replacement (reserve) and transformational exercises, developed the conditions of recommended sample assignments and recommended their use in educational practice .

3. The stage of communicative practice of developing linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators. The purpose of this stage is to further develop the linguistic and cultural skills of production and receptive foreign language, to correct and correct those formed in the previous stages as much as possible, to move from communicative skills to grammatical skills. At this stage, communicative tasks for the use of grammatical events activated depending on the speech situation prevail.

4. Control stage of development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators. This stage included the collection and analysis of data on the level of formation of students' linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, as well as the results of their own assessment of the learned grammatical material. In order to achieve the most reliable results in the process of conducting the research, according to the complexity of tasks of different levels of control: tests, discussions, group discussions, formal and role-playing games, the preparation of projects was recommended and used in practice, students' linguistic, cultural and communicative skills allowed a differential approach to control, taking into account the level of competence development [2].

The indicators of the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence in future translators were defined as consisting of 4: cognitive, operational-activity, motivational and reflexive criteria.

The question of the phenomenal nature of speech competence, description and determination of its tasks is relevant in modern science. A.N. Ksenofontova first recommended her observations to the scientific community in this direction in language education. After that, we observed that M. P. Manayenkova also distinguished the following tasks of speech competence: knowledge acquisition (expression), information (message, expression), communicative (effect), stimulating (motivational) [4]. At the same time, based on the fact that in the real process all tasks are interrelated and can pass to each other, we focused on each of them separately:

a) the function of speech competence to acquire knowledge is, on the one hand, a tool of thinking, and on the other hand, a product of mental activity, and it is especially closely related to the role of speech in the realization of higher mental tasks of a person. Speech is the main tool in educational activities, which allows the teacher to organize and implement it both in the classroom and outside the school.

b) the information function of speech competence is related to the transfer and delivery of information (knowledge acquisition, mastery skills) in the educational process and creating a favorable environment for the success of the pedagogical process. The information task of speech activity also includes the information task of speech competence, which consists in making the information received by students have a personal meaning. The value of information increases depending on how important it is in practice. The validity and reliability of this opinion has been fully confirmed in the test fields of the

research and in the pedagogical practice of future English language teachers. During the period of pedagogy, students not only applied their knowledge and skills, but also used the theoretical information received in lectures and seminars on psychological and pedagogical sciences and methods of teaching various subjects in written and oral presentations of students. They used it in the analysis of their activities in the classroom. Thus, the conclusion that the informational function of speech competence is not only the ability of students of the field to receive information, but also the competence approach - the application of the received information in their own activities was substantiated.

c) the communicative task of speech competence is to be able to choose the means of speech adequately for the current pedagogical situation. First of all, this is due to the diversity of the arsenal of speech skills and the adequacy of their selection in relation to the current situation.

g) the stimulating (motivational) function of speech competence is determined by a profession-oriented attitude. The chosen professional activity style of the teacher is also expressed in speech activity. Speech competence determines the direction of the teacher's personality, that is, the set of needs and motives that determine the main direction of the person's behavior. The motivational function of speech competence is manifested in speech behavior. The direction of speech behavior depends on the level of formation of speech competence of the pedagogue. Depending on the teacher's values in the pedagogical activity, he chooses speech tools that put the student in a certain position. If the importance of the teacher in the pedagogical activity is to place the student in a subjective position with the help of speech skills, then this will be a high indicator of his speech skills.

Summarizing the opinions of the world scientific-methodical literature on the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence in future translators, we decided to put forward the scientific opinion that the structure of speech competence occurs as a sum of the following three components: that is:

- a) characterized by a motivational and purposeful approach related to the socio-practical direction of activity;
- b) is characterized by the presence of a complex of knowledge and skills aimed at the speech of a meaningful, specific activity, in this case the competence approach takes the lead;
- c) determined by the potential of personal, professionally significant psychological qualities of the subject, which implies an acmeological approach.

In the process of conducting experimental work, it was found that the use of the following methods is effective in developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators:

The interview method is to help future translators to understand that they have certain skills regarding linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, to study their opinions on the development of these skills in young people, and to ensure that they think freely and independently about the problem. will give.

The question-and-answer method serves to determine the personal opinions and views of future translators about linguistic, cultural and communicative competence. Clear, concise and well-worded questions allow students to think logically.

The method of the lecture is to explain the essence of communicative competence to the participants of the experiment, to explain its dictionary meaning correctly, about the factors, conditions and pedagogical possibilities of forming the spoken feeling in the person. directed to provide information.

The method of explanation is the formation of an attitude about the theoretical essence of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators and the social importance of having it.

On the basis of the method of practice (practical exercises) - intellectual training, conditions are created for the development of intercultural communication among students.

Interactive methods - free and independent thinking on the part of intercultural communication by students, education of the skills and competence of organizing a debate, liberation of students from standard thinking, as well as an opportunity to collect various ideas regarding the solution of the discussed problem will give.

The expert evaluation method helps to ensure impartial, objective, comprehensively correct evaluation of the activities of event participants (respondents) by peers or by a specially designated group of experts.

The method of creating problem situations provides future translators with the ability to think seriously about the research problem and the basic concepts that illuminate its essence, and to use the available intellectual opportunities to find a solution to the problem.

The method of working with the source is the correct and complete understanding by students of the concept of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence, the ability to organize small research activities on the questions and problem situations brought to their attention. helps them.

Demonstration method - creates the necessary conditions for strengthening the theoretical information acquired by students, for the full understanding of the essence of linguistic, cultural and communicative skills, and for training the skills of applying knowledge in practice.

The method of practical experiments (research) is to think logically on the topics brought to the attention of students, to put forward personal opinions, to prove and defend their views, to convince their peers, and to help them develop their skills and abilities. creates the necessary conditions for a deep understanding of its essence [3].

CONCLUSION. The approach of linguistic and cultural studies was chosen as the theoretical and methodological basis for the development of the system for the development of linguistic and cultural and communicative competence of future translators. The approach of linguistics and culture is the unity of language and culture, and includes the expression of culture through language and speech.

In conclusion, the process of developing the linguistic, cultural and communicative competence of future translators is based on the clear and correct implementation of the sequence of complex pedagogical systems. In this sense, it is necessary to organize education aimed at the development of linguistic, cultural and communicative competence on the basis of interactive methods and educational technologies.

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